

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO v512

Thermal Energy for Space Heating, Air Conditioning and Removal of Humidity in Residential Buildings in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv

Joseph Nowarski, M.Sc., ME – Energy Conservation Expert

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Abstract

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization (BESOO) is a system of online internet programs that calculates temperatures, energy, and other parameters for various cases and conditions based on input values.

The current version is for ambient temperature, relative humidity, and solar radiation in Jerusalem and in Tel Aviv. Jerusalem has lower humidity and colder winter. Tel Aviv has moderate temperatures but higher humidity.

The program allows selection of building orientation every 22.5 degrees. It calculates temperatures of the outside wall layers, room air temperature, optional ventilation, and thermal energy required for space heating, cooling, and air conditioning condense. The calculations are for various building designs. In addition, the program calculates Thermal Time Constant, TTC, based on the input data.

The program may be useful for selection of optimum building design, like the location and thickness of insulation and thermal mass of the concrete layer.

The online internet program according to this work is available on nowagreen.com/BESO (free, no login required).

Glossary

AbF	absorption coefficient of solar energy on building wall [1]
Ave	average
CFdir	conversion factor from global radiation on horizontal surface to selected tilt angle and direction [4]
dir	outside wall direction
dtau	time period of the integration = integration interval, sec
Ecool	thermal energy for space cooling [J]
Edry	thermal energy to remove humidity from room air by cooling [J]
Eheat	thermal energy for space heating [J]
H	height of the room, m
Hfloor	height between floors, m
Lo1	floor length of outside wall part 1, m
Lout1	outside length of outside wall part 1, m
mW	mass of condense (water) [gram]
PS	Polystyrene Foam
RH	relative humidity of air
Ref	reference
SE	solar global radiation on horizontal surface, W/m ²
SEdir	solar radiation on vertical surface in direction <i>dir</i> , W/m ²
SEo	solar energy absorbed by outside wall, Ws/m ²
Ta	ambient (outside) air temperature, °C
Tr	room air temperature, °C
TTC	Thermal Time Constant, hours

Energy Units

This work is in metric units. Energy is expressed in Joule and power in Watts. Time is GMT+2 for the whole year, DST is not considered.

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization Program

The current version is based on publications “*Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO v101*” [7] and “*Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO v201*” [8].

The BESOO program was successfully validated in the publication [7] using Thermal Time Constant (TTC) method.

Versions described in [7] and [8] applied fix ambient temperature and the same solar radiation as on 23 December 2024 in Jerusalem for 10 days.

The current version (512) applies actual ambient air temperature, air relative humidity, and solar global radiation in Jerusalem and Tel Aviv in the years 2023-2024 and is dedicated to calculations of thermal energy for space heating, air conditioning, and removal of humidity from the air.

Ambient Air Temperature, Relative Humidity, and Solar Radiation Datasets

Ambient air temperature, air relative humidity (RH), and solar global radiation datasets for Jerusalem and Tel Aviv are from the internet site [6]. The records are every 10 minutes. The datasets are for the years 2023 and 2024.

Global solar radiation is multiplied by conversion factors according to the direction of the outside wall, month and hour. The conversion factor is from the internet site [4].

Starting the simulation on 1st January midnight involves a big difference between the ambient air temperature and room air temperature. To avoid a long period of stabilization of the simulation results (depending on the Thermal Time Constant – TTC of the building), the simulation starts on 30 April or 31 May.

For Jerusalem the simulation starts on 31 May while on the first day of the simulation the ambient air temperature is set to the 15-31 May average until the same actual ambient temperature.

For Tel Aviv the simulation starts on 30 April while on the first day of the simulation the ambient air temperature is set to the daily average until the same actual ambient temperature.

The Building and the Apartment

The calculations are for the entire apartment and not for individual rooms; the entire apartment is considered one room.

It is assumed that the room temperature in all neighboring apartments is the same as in the tested apartment.

Chart 1 - Building and apartment

- Lo1 floor length of outside wall part 1, m
- Lout1 outside length of outside wall part 1, m
- Lo2 floor length of outside wall part 1, m
- Lout2 outside length of outside wall part 1, m

$$Lout = Lo + (0.3 + 0.23)/2 \text{ [m]}$$

- 0.3 typical thickness of outside wall in residential buildings in Israel [m]
- 0.23 typical thickness of neighboring wall in residential buildings in Israel [m]

Outside Wall Layers

The heat flow is from outside the building to inside. In cases where the heat flow is in the opposite direction, the value of the heat flow [Q] is negative.

Table 1 - Outside wall layers

Layer #	Layer	Material
Outside air		
0	Outside laminar layer	
1	Outer layer	Stones + Cement Base
2	Outside insulation	Polystyrene Foam (PS)
3	Central layer	Concrete
4	Inside insulation	Polystyrene Foam
5	Inner layer	Gypsum Plaster
6	Inside laminar layer	
Room air		

Table 2 - Outside wall layers data for Jerusalem

Layer #	Layer	Material	Thickness	Density	Specific Heat	Thermal Conductivity	Thermal Resistance	Ref
Units			m	kg/m3	J/kg,°C	W/m,°C	m2,°C/W	
			Th	Rho	cp	λ	r	
Outside air								
0	Outside laminar layer						0.040	[5]
1	Outer layer	Stones + Cement Base	0.100	2120	860	1.4420	0.069	[2]
2	Outside insulation	PS	0.020	30	1440	0.0320	0.625	[2]
3	Central layer	Concrete	0.200	2400	970	2.1000	0.095	[5]
4	Inside insulation	PS	0.000	30	1440	0.0320	0.000	[2]
5	Inner layer	Gypsum Plaster	0.015	1200	1080	0.3500	0.043	[5]
6	Inside laminar layer						0.145	[5]
Room air								
Total			0.335		940		1.017	

Table 3 - Outside wall layers data Tel Aviv

Layer #	Layer	Material	Thickness	Density	Specific Heat	Thermal Conductivity	Thermal Resistance	Ref
Units			m	kg/m3	J/kg,°C	W/m,°C	m2,°C/W	
			Th	Rho	cp	λ	r	
Outside air								
0	Outside laminar layer						0.040	[5]
1	Outer layer	Stones + Cement Base	0.050	2120	860	1.4420	0.035	[2]
2	Outside insulation	PS	0.000	30	1440	0.0320	0.000	[2]
3	Central layer	Concrete	0.160	2400	970	2.1000	0.076	[5]
4	Ytong	Ytong 045	0.090	475	1000	0.1500	0.600	[2]
5	Inner layer	Gypsum Plaster	0.015	1200	1080	0.3500	0.043	[5]
6	Inside laminar layer						0.145	[5]
Room air								
Total			0.315		955	1.327	0.939	

Outside Walls Orientation

The input page of the program allows selection of directions of both walls of the apartment. The direction step is every 22.5° (like North and North-North-East).

Infiltration

The default value of infiltration is 0.1 changes per hour, which means that every hour 0.1 (10%) of the apartment air volume is replaced by the outside ambient air (fresh air).

Ventilation

Ventilation is by opening windows. The simulation default values to open the windows for ventilation are:

- In winter, when the ambient air temperature (T_a) is above 21°C and 1°C higher than the room air temperature (T_r)
- In summer, when the ambient air temperature (T_a) is below 24°C and 1°C lower than the room air temperature (T_r)

The amount of fresh air for ventilation is also expressed in the number of air changes per hour. The default value in the simulation is 10.

Input Parameters and Default Values

Table 4 - Input parameters and default values in Jerusalem

choose direction of part 1:	East ▾
choose direction of part 2:	South ▾
Heat On temperature	18 °C
Cool On temperature	26 °C
infiltration - number of changes per hour	0.1 V/hr
ventilation - number of changes per hour	10 V/hr
Winter ventilation ambient temperature (T_a) >	21 °C
Winter Δ ($T_a - T_{room}$) >	1 °C
Summer ventilation T_a <	24 °C
Summer Δ ($T_{room} - T_a$) >	1 °C
height between floors (outside)	3.00 m
room height (inside)	2.65 m
floor length of outside wall part 1	10 m
floor length of outside wall part 2	10 m
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.100 m
outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.020 m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.200 m
inner insulation layer (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0 m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	0.015 m

Table 5 - Input parameters and default values in Tel Aviv

choose direction of part 1:

choose direction of part 2:

Heat On temperature	18 °C
Cool On temperature	26 °C
infiltration - number of changes per hour	0.1 V/hr
ventilation - number of changes per hour	10 V/hr
Winter ventilation ambient temperature (Ta) >	21 °C
Winter Δ (Ta - Troom) >	1 °C
Summer ventilation Ta <	24 °C
Summer Δ (Troom - Ta) >	1 °C
height between floors (outside)	3.00 m
room height (inside)	2.65 m
floor length of outside wall part 1	10 m
floor length of outside wall part 2	10 m
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.050 m
outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0 m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.160 m
layer (4) Ytong thickness	0.090 m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	0.015 m

Fix Parameters

Table 6 - Fix parameters part 1

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Integration Interval	dtau	10	seconds
air density	RhoA	1.204529	kg/m ³
air specific heat	cpa	1007	J/kg,°C
absorption coefficient of solar radiation on building walls	AbF	0.53	

Table 7 - Fix parameters part 2 for Jerusalem

layer	material	Rho [kg/m ³]	λ [W/m,°C]	cp [J/kg,°C]
layer 1	stone+cement	2120	1.442	860
layer 2	outer insulation PS	30	0.032	1440
layer 3	concrete	2400	2.1	970
layer 4	inner insulation PS	30	0.032	1440
layer 5	inner plaster	1200	0.35	1080

Table 8 - Fix parameters part 2 for Tel Aviv

layer	material	Rho [kg/m ³]	λ [W/m·°C]	cp [J/kg,°C]
layer 1	stone+cement	2120	1.442	860
layer 2	outer insulation PS	30	0.032	1440
layer 3	concrete	2400	2.1	970
layer 4	inner insulation Ytong 045	475	0.15	1000
layer 5	inner plaster	1200	0.35	1080

Initial Values

Table 9 - Initial values for Jerusalem

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
initial room air temperature	Troom	21.2	°C
initial temperatures of all layers of the outside wall	To1, To3, To5	21.2	°C

The initial temperature of outside wall layers is the initial room air temperature, which is the average of ambient air temperature in the period 15-31 May 2023 – 21.2°C.

Table 10 - Initial values for Tel Aviv

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
initial room air temperature	Troom	18.4	°C
initial temperatures of all layers of the outside wall	To1, To3, To5	18.4	°C

The initial temperature of the outside wall layers is the initial room air temperature, which is the average of ambient air temperature on 30 April 2023 – 18.4°C.

Energy Calculations

In general, energy calculations in this simulation are related to the following aspects:

- conduction heat transfer through the outside wall layers
- absorption of solar energy by the outer layer of outside walls
- changes in the thermal mass of the outside wall layers
- mix of room air with fresh air by infiltration and ventilation
- thermal energy for condense during cooling

All cases involve “*temperature difference*” (dt , ΔT , Δt). There is a different meaning of dt (Δt) in the case of conduction heat transfer and the case of change in the thermal mass of the wall layer or of the room air temperature.

In the case of conduction, dt (Δt) is the difference between the temperature at the starting point of the heat flow and the endpoint.

In case of a change in the thermal mass of the body, dt (Δt) is the change in the body temperature at the same point (like the middle of the wall layer).

To distinguish between conduction and thermal mass, the energy related to the conduction heat flow will be indicated in this work as “ Q ” and the change in the thermal mass of the body as “ E ”.

The radiation heat transfer (like radiation from outside walls to outer space at night) is not included in this version.

Conduction Heat Transfer between Layers

This issue is described in detail in publication [7].

Formula 1 - Heat transfer through multi-layer building element

$$Q = U * A * (t_{hi} - t_{low})$$

Q overall heat transfer through multi-layer building element (like few layers of outside wall) [W]

- U overall coefficient of heat transfer [W/m²,°C]
- A area normal to the flow (like outside wall total area) [m²]
- $(t_{hi} - t_{low})$ temperature difference between the start point of the heat flow and the end point [°C]

Table 11 - Conduction heat flow between layers

Q	from	to	From	to
Qo1	Outside air	Center of layer 1	Ta	To1
Qo3	Center of layer 1	Center of layer 3	To1	To3
Qo5	Center of layer 3	Center of layer 5	To3	To5
QoR	Center of layer 5	Room air	To5	Tr

Energy Flow between Layers

This issue is described in detail in publication [7].

Formula 2 - Change in layer's temperature

$$dt = (Q_{in} - Q_{out}) * d\tau / MC$$

$$Q_{in} = q_{in} * A$$

$$Q_{out} = q_{out} * A$$

$$MC = M * c_p$$

$$M = A * Th * Rho$$

- A area of the layer [m²]
- c_p specific heat at constant pressure [J/kg,°C]
- dt temperature increase of the layer [°C] in period $d\tau$
- $d\tau$ integration interval [sec]
- M mass of the layer [kg]
- q_{in} energy flow into the layer [W/m²]
- q_{out} energy flow out from the layer [W/m²]
- Rho density of the material of the layer (like concrete) [kg/m³]
- Th thickness of the layer [m]

Table 12 - Change in thermal energy of outside wall layers

Layer #	Material	E	Q _{in}	Q _{out}	Temperature
1	Stones + Cement Base	$E_{o1} = Q_{o1} + SE_o - Q_{o3}$	$Q_{o1} + SE_o$	Q_{o3}	$To1$
3	Concrete	$E_{o3} = Q_{o3} - Q_{o5}$	Q_{o3}	Q_{o5}	$To3$
5	Gypsum Plaster	$E_{o5} = Q_{o5} - Q_{oR}$	Q_5	Q_{oR}	$To5$

Solar Energy Absorbed by Outer Layer of Outside Wall (Layer 1)

Formula 3 - Solar energy absorbed by outer layer of outside wall (Layer 1)

$$SE_o = SE_{o\text{dir}1} + SE_{o\text{dir}2}$$

$$SE_{o\text{dir}1} = SE * A_{out1} * CF_{dir1} * AbF$$

$$SE_{o\text{dir}2} = SE * A_{out2} * CF_{dir2} * AbF$$

- SE_o solar energy absorbed by Layer 1, W
- $SE_{o\text{dir}1}$ solar energy absorbed by part 1 of outside wall Layer 1 in direction $dir1$ (like East), W
- $SE_{o\text{dir}2}$ solar energy absorbed by part 2 of outside wall Layer 1 in direction $dir2$ (like South), W
- SE solar global radiation on horizontal surface, W/m² [6]
- A_{out1} outside area of part 1 of the external wall in direction $dir1$ (like East)
- A_{out2} outside area of part 2 of the external wall in direction $dir2$ (like South)
- CF_{dir} conversion factor from global radiation on horizontal surface to selected tilt angle and direction [4]
- AbF solar absorption coefficient, absorption coefficient of solar radiation on building wall [1]

$$AbF = 0.53$$

The solar absorption coefficient (AbF) depends on many factors and its determination is much beyond the scope of this work. The current version applies $AbF=0.53$ as in the original BESO program [1].

Direction conversion factor, CF_{dir} , changes every hour and every month, while global solar energy changes every 10 minutes and every day.

Energy Flow in Outer Layer (Layer 1)

Calculations of thermal energy of room air are based on Formula 2:

$$dt = (Q_{in} - Q_{out}) * dtau / MC$$

$$Q_{in} = Q_{o1} + SE_o$$

$$Q_{out} = Q_{o3}$$

Formula 4 - Outer layer (Layer 1) temperature change

$$dt = (Q_{o1} + SE_o - Q_{o3}) * dtau / MC1$$

dt	temperature increase of Layer 1 in $dtau$ period [°C]
Q_{in}	thermal energy entering Layer 1 [W]
Q_{out}	thermal energy leaving Layer 1 [W]
$dtau$	integration interval [sec]
Q_{o1}	conduction heat flow from outside air to the center of outer layer (Layer 1) [W]
Q_{o3}	conduction heat flow from the center of outer layer (Layer 1) to the center of central layer (Layer 3) [W]
SE_o	solar energy absorbed by outer layer [W]
$MC1$	MC of Layer 1 [J/°C,m2]

Building Energy Simulation

This issue is described in detail in publication [7].

Formula 5 - Conduction heat transfer through outside wall layers (Q), W/°C [7]

$$Q = U * A * (t_{hi} - t_{low})$$

$$Q_{o1} = UA_{o1} * (T_a - T_{o1})$$

$$Q_{o3} = UA_{o3} * (T_{o1} - T_{o3})$$

$$Q_{o5} = UA_{o5} * (T_{o3} - T_{o5})$$

$$Q_{oR} = UA_{oR} * (T_{o5} - T_r)$$

Formula 6 - Simulation of temperature

In the programming language, the simulation of the temperature has the following form:

$$T_{new} = T_{last} + dt$$

T_{new}	new temperature of the body [°C]
T_{last}	last temperature of the body [°C]
dt	temperature increase of the body [°C] in period $d\tau$

Integration Interval

The best integration interval, $d\tau$, for this simulation is 0.5 second. Application of this integration interval takes big amount of the internet host resources which causes serious delays.

Considering the internet host and the PC performance, the integration interval selected for this version is 10 seconds, which results in 0.21% loss of accuracy.

Room Air Temperature Change

This issue is described in detail in publication [7].

$$dt = (Q_{in} - Q_{out}) * d\tau / MC \quad [7: \text{Formula 3}]$$

In the current version Q_{in} is the heat transfer from the last layer of the outside wall, Layer 5, heat of infiltration air and heat of ventilation air.

Formula 7 - Room air temperature change by the heat transfer from the last outside wall layer

$$T_{new} = T_{last} + Q_{oR} * dtau / MCa$$

Q_{oR} conduction heat flow from the center of inner layer (Layer 5) to the room air [W]

$dtau$ Integration Interval [sec]

MCa thermal mass of the air in the room [J/°C]

$$MCa = Ma * cpa$$

$$Ma = Va * RhoA$$

Ma mass of the air in the room [kg]

Va volume of the air in the room [m³]

$RhoA$ density of the air in the room [kg/m³]

cpa specific heat of the air in the room [J/kg,°C]

$$cpa = 1,007 \text{ J/kg,}^\circ\text{C} \quad [7]$$

$$RhoA = 1.205 \text{ kg/m}^3 \quad [7]$$

Formula 8 - Room air temperature change by infiltration

$$T_{new} = (infiltration * dtau * Ta + T_{last} * (Rvol - infiltration * dtau)) / Rvol$$

$$infiltration = (Infiltration \text{ Changes/hr}) / 3600 \text{ sec/hr [m}^3\text{/sec]}$$

Ta ambient air temperature [°C]

$Rvol$ room air volume [m³]

Formula 9 - Room air temperature change by ventilation

$$T_{new} = (ventilation * dtau * Ta + T_{last} * (Rvol - ventilation * dtau)) / Rvol$$

$$ventilation = (Ventilation \text{ Changes/hr}) / 3600 \text{ sec/hr [m}^3\text{/sec]}$$

Amount of Water Condensed During Cooling

Formula 10 - Mass of condensed water during cooling

$$\Delta mW = mW1 - mW2$$

$$mW1 = ((RH/100) * 216.7 * (6.1078 * 10^{((7.5*TrLast) / (237.3+ TrLast))}) / (TrLast+273.15)$$

$$mW2 = ((RH/100) * 216.7 * (6.1078 * 10^{((7.5*Tr) / (237.3+ Tr))}) / (Tr+273.15)$$

ΔmW	mass of condensed water during cooling [g/m ³]
$mW1$	mass of water in room air before cooling [g/m ³]
$mW2$	mass of water in room air after cooling [g/m ³]
RH	current room air relative humidity (RH) [%]
$TrLast$	room air temperature before cooling [°C]
Tr	room air temperature after cooling [°C]

Thermal Energy of Room Air Condense

Formula 11 - Thermal energy of room air condense

$$Edry = \Delta mW * Lv$$

$$Lv = 2477.2 \text{ J/g [10]}$$

$Edry$	thermal energy of room air condense [J/m ³]
ΔmW	mass of condensed water during cooling [g/m ³]
Lv	latent heat of water at 10°C [J/g]

Simulation Results

In this version the simulation results are in the following forms:

- Main table on the internet results page. This table includes more than 52,000 lines showing some results every 10 minutes and others every hour
- Results table at the end of the internet results page
- CSV files:
 - CSV file with the 10 minutes results as on the internet page in the original resolution (more precise). The data in this file are related to the last Integration Interval ($d\tau$) cycle and are not the 10 minutes averages or totals.
 - hourly results
 - daily results

The CSV files may be downloaded from the internet results page.

Table 13 - Example of main table on the internet results page (52,848 lines)

day #	date	hour	Ta °C	RH %	SE W/m2	SE Gain W	To1 °C	To3 °C	To5 °C	Tr °C	QoR [W]	Heat Whth/hr	Dry Whth/hr	vent s/hr
74	20230813	10:00	34.8	39	837	16666	41.799	26.895	26.61	26	194.269	-254	290	
74	20230813	10:10	35.2	36	857	17065	42.482	26.918	26.625	26	198.922			
74	20230813	10:20	35.4	37	869	17304	43.155	26.941	26.64	26	203.812			
74	20230813	10:30	36.3	34	887	17662	43.858	26.966	26.656	26	208.939			
74	20230813	10:40	35.8	33	909	18100	44.532	26.991	26.673	26	214.303			
74	20230813	10:50	37	31	919	18299	45.237	27.018	26.691	26	219.903			
74	20230813	11:00	36.8	29	924	17343	45.843	27.045	26.709	26	225.737	-299	276	
74	20230813	11:10	37.5	28	928	17418	46.455	27.074	26.728	26	231.791			
74	20230813	11:20	37.9	27	934	17531	47.062	27.103	26.748	26	238.056			
74	20230813	11:30	38.1	26	939	17625	47.654	27.133	26.768	26	244.524			
74	20230813	11:40	38.1	23	949	17812	48.229	27.164	26.789	26	251.188			
74	20230813	11:50	37.8	22	953	17887	48.77	27.196	26.811	26	258.041			
day #	date	hour	Ta °C	RH %	SE W/m2	SE Gain W	To1 °C	To3 °C	To5 °C	Tr °C	QoR [W]	Heat Whth/hr	Dry Whth/hr	vent s/hr

Description of columns:

- day # simulation day number starting with 0
- date date of ambient temperature and solar radiation data, 8 digits – yyyymmdd
- hour hour:minute of ambient temperature and solar radiation data
- Ta ambient air temperature [°C]
- RH relative humidity [%]
- SE global solar radiation [W/m2]
- SE Gain gain of solar radiation of the building outside walls [W]
- To1 temperature at the middle of Layer 1, outer layer [°C]
- To3 temperature at the middle of Layer 3, central layer [°C]
- To5 temperature at the middle of Layer 5, inner layer [°C]
- Tr room air temperature [°C]

- QoR conduction heat transfer from the middles of Layer 5 to the room air [W]
- Heat >0 thermal energy for space heating [Wh thermal /hr]
- Heat <0 thermal energy for cooling – decrease of room air temperature (without condense) [Wh thermal /hr]
- Dry thermal energy for condense during cooling [Wh thermal /hr]
- vent ventilation time [sec/hr]

The results in this table are related to the last Integration Interval (*dtau*) cycle and are not the 10 minutes averages or totals.

Table 14 - Main results table at the end of the internet results page

28/08/2025 02:54:25 GMT			
nowagreen.com BESOO page 512Jm, v512Jm.01 AC, Outside walls + Ta + RH + SE + Infiltration + Ventilation only, dtau=10 sec			
page / version	512Jm	512Jm.01	AC
URL	https://nowagreen.com/BESO/512Jm		
Integration Interval	10	sec	dtau
Thermal Time Constant	109.61	hours	TTC
start day	20230531		
last day	20240531		
simulation days	367		
Ave ambient air temperature in the simulation period	18.59	°C	
Ave ambient air RH in the simulation period	62%	°C	
simulation hours	8808		100%
heating hours in the simulation period	1474		17%
cooling hours in the simulation period	1098		12%
comfort hours in the simulation period	6235		71%
heating start date	20231129		
heating end date	20240326		
Ave ambient air temperature in heating period	11.8	°C	
Ave ambient air RH in heating period	70%		
thermal energy for heating	304	kWh thermal	29%
cooling start date	20230602		
cooling end date	20231108		
Ave ambient air temperature in cooling period	23.67	°C	
Ave ambient air RH in cooling period	58%		
thermal energy for cooling (change of room air temperature)	365	kWh thermal	35%
quantity of condense during cooling	539	liter of water	
cooling energy for condense	371	kWh thermal	36%
thermal energy for cooling and for condense	736	kWh thermal	71%
total energy for heating, cooling and condense	1040	kWh thermal	
total ventilation time	598	hours	7%
comfort hours without ventilation	5637	hours	64%
Max values			
Max Heat power [W thermal]	626	20240203	8:40
Max Cool power [W thermal]	749	20230908	19:40
Max power for condense [W thermal]	1340	20230813	20:10
Max power for cooling and for condense	2089	W thermal	

Table 15 - Example of CSV file with the 10 minutes results

The data in this file are related to the last Integration Interval (*dtau*) cycle and are not the 10 minutes averages or totals.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
1	nowagreen.com BESOO page 512]m v512]rOutside Wall28/08/202 dtau=10 sec																
2	please note that the data in this file are related to the last Integration Interval (dtau) cycle and are not the 10 minutes averages or totals																
3	day	date	hr	min	Ta	RH	SE [W/m	Solar Gain [To1	To3	To5	Tr	QoR [W]	Heat [W]	Cold [W]	Dry (conde	condense [g/second]
10768	74	20230813	18	0	29	78	45	918.075938	42.77719	28.24118	27.56639	26	498.7666	0	-522.745	1130.6928	0.456439844
10769	74	20230813	18	10	28	80	25	510.042188	42.10549	28.25442	27.57711	26	502.1851	0	-520.803	1155.3755	0.466403796
10770	74	20230813	18	20	28	82	10	204.016875	41.43938	28.26639	27.58696	26	505.326	0	-521.264	1185.307	0.478486612
10771	74	20230813	18	30	27	84	2	40.803375	40.7736	28.27708	27.59592	26	508.1849	0	-519.656	1210.4698	0.488644364
10772	74	20230813	18	40	27	85	0	0	40.11985	28.28652	27.604	26	510.7609	0	-518.658	1222.5279	0.493511992
10773	74	20230813	18	50	27	87	0	0	39.48864	28.29476	27.61119	26	513.057	0	-519.167	1252.5216	0.50561991
10774	74	20230813	19	0	27	87	0	0	38.87889	28.30183	27.61753	26	515.0794	0	-519.402	1253.0898	0.505849279
10775	74	20230813	19	10	26	88	0	0	38.29387	28.30779	27.62304	26	516.8367	0	-520.266	1269.6014	0.512514696
10776	74	20230813	19	20	26	89	0	0	37.7238	28.31268	27.62774	26	518.3385	0	-519.088	1281.1195	0.517164334
10777	74	20230813	19	30	26	91	0	0	37.15935	28.31653	27.63167	26	519.5934	0	-515.876	1301.8013	0.525513214
10778	74	20230813	19	40	26	92	0	0	36.62177	28.31938	27.63484	26	520.6089	0	-516.891	1318.6979	0.532334032
10779	74	20230813	19	50	26	92	0	0	36.10548	28.32126	27.6373	26	521.394	0	-516.783	1318.4212	0.53222235
10780	74	20230813	20	0	25	93	0	0	35.60514	28.32224	27.63906	26	521.9581	0	-515.561	1329.5978	0.53673415
10781	74	20230813	20	10	25	94	0	0	35.12001	28.32233	27.64015	26	522.31	0	-514.126	1340.1537	0.540995353
10782	74	20230813	20	20	25	93	0	0	34.66226	28.32158	27.64061	26	522.4585	0	-515.168	1328.5842	0.536324976
10783	74	20230813	20	30	25	94	0	0	34.21767	28.32001	27.63855	25.98553	522.5294	0	-515.168	1328.5842	0.536324976
10784	74	20230813	20	40	25	94	0	0	33.79423	28.31766	27.63677	25.99812	526.9808	0	-515.168	1328.5842	0.536324976

Description of columns:

- Ta ambient (outside) air temperature [°C]
- RH relative humidity [%]
- SE global solar radiation [W/m2]
- SE Gain gain of solar radiation of the building outside walls [W]
- Heat thermal energy for space heating [W]
- Cold thermal energy for cooling [W]
- Dry thermal energy for condense [W]
- condense quantity of condense [g/sec]

Table 16 - Example of CSV file with hourly results

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	nowag	v512	m.0	Outside v	dtau=10 sec				
2	day	date	Hr	min	Heat [J/hr]	Cool [J/hr]	Condense	Dry (conc)	Ventilation [seconds/hr]
1779	74	20230813	0	0	0	0	0	0	3230
1780	74	20230813	1	0	0	0	0	0	2750
1781	74	20230813	2	0	0	0	0	0	2350
1782	74	20230813	3	0	0	0	0	0	2690
1783	74	20230813	4	0	0	0	0	0	1980
1784	74	20230813	5	0	0	0	0	0	1460
1785	74	20230813	6	0	0	0	0	0	1450
1786	74	20230813	7	0	0	0	0	0	840
1787	74	20230813	8	0	0	-553712	394.0259	976081.1	0
1788	74	20230813	9	0	0	-778201	460.1224	1139815	0
1789	74	20230813	10	0	0	-913251	421.4889	1044112	0
1790	74	20230813	11	0	0	-1077646	400.5026	992125	0
1791	74	20230813	12	0	0	-1263952	350.3037	867772.4	0
1792	74	20230813	13	0	0	-1456602	303.2651	751248.2	0
1793	74	20230813	14	0	0	-1562674	724.4279	1794553	0
1794	74	20230813	15	0	0	-1658396	990.1608	2452826	0
1795	74	20230813	16	0	0	-1769194	1149.174	2846733	0
1796	74	20230813	17	0	0	-1851408	1333.662	3303747	0
1797	74	20230813	18	0	0	-1880551	1540.112	3815167	0
1798	74	20230813	19	0	0	-1866643	1758.677	4356595	0
1799	74	20230813	20	0	0	-1860722	1891.913	4686646	0
1800	74	20230813	21	0	0	-1233005	1283.643	3179839	690
1801	74	20230813	22	0	0	0	0	0	2650
1802	74	20230813	23	0	0	0	0	0	2690

Table 17 - Example of CSV file with daily results

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	nowagree	v512	m.0	Outside v	dtau=10 sec		
2	day	date	Heat [J/d]	Cool [J/da]	Condense	Dry (conc)	Ventilation [seconds/day]
69	66	20230805	0	-6284554	3704.672	9177213	18920
70	67	20230806	0	-11806210	3909.013	9683407	19080
71	68	20230807	0	-16615138	6428.25	15924061	30310
72	69	20230808	0	-9502788	5426.105	13441548	23360
73	70	20230809	0	-7177498	4237.933	10498207	18100
74	71	20230810	0	-6617682	4044.026	10017862	16740
75	72	20230811	0	-7265555	4241.477	10506987	14940
76	73	20230812	0	-10259980	6291.989	15586515	17860
77	74	20230813	0	-19725956	13001.48	32207260	22780
78	75	20230814	0	-14029085	11424.23	28300110	33640
79	76	20230815	0	-8564840	6206.882	15375689	30010

Examples of Application

Chart 2 - Tel Aviv: thermal energy for space heating (Heat), cooling (Cool) and condense (Dry) [kWh thermal/d]

Chart 3 - Jerusalem: thermal energy for space heating (Heat), cooling (Cool) and condense (Dry) [kWh thermal/d]

BESOO Website

This version of the Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization is available online (free, no need to login) on:

<https://nowagreen.com/BESO/512Jm>

<https://nowagreen.com/BESO/512TA>

Changes in this Version

Glossary:

- description of Ecoool, Edry corrected
- CoolHr, HotHr removed

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